

**Nomenclatural corrections for two genus-group names of Lycaenidae
(Lepidoptera)**

Zsolt BÁLINT

*Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum,
Department of Zoology, Lepidoptera Collection, H-1088 Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary.*

E-mail: balint.zsolt@nhmus.hu

Abstract – *Moseralfia* nom. nov. is proposed as a replacement name for *Moseria* Bálint, 2022 (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae), a junior homonym of four available generic names, of which *Moseria* Ghigi, 1909 (Ctenophora: Pleurobrachiidae) is the oldest and currently valid. *Szentivanya* Bálint, 2022 (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae) is a junior homonym of *Szentivanya* Kaszab, 1958 (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae); as it is also a junior objective synonym of *Pseudogyris* Braby et Müller, 2022, no action is needed.

Key words – homonym, replacement name, synonym, type species

INTRODUCTION

The fourth part of the book series “Pillangóvilág” (World Butterflies) (D’ABRERA & BÁLINT 2022) was published on 30 September 2022 (BÁLINT 2022). The volume includes an Appendix with descriptions of several new species-, genus- and family-group names that were mentioned in the main body of the text (BÁLINT 2022). Two genus-group names proposed in the family Lycaenidae turned out to be homonymous; they are corrected in the present short contribution.

NOMENCLATURAL CORRECTIONS

***Moseralfia* nom. nov.**

Moseria Bálint, 2022 (BÁLINT 2022: 97). Type species by original designation: *Thecla celelata* Hewitson, 1874. Junior homonym of *Moseria* Ghigi, 1909 (Ctenophora: Pleurobrachiidae), *Moseria* Weise, 1922 (Coleoptera:

Chrysomelidae), *Moseria* Totton, 1965 (Cnidaria: Resomiidae) and *Moseria* Beer et Nucifora, 1965 (Acari: Tarsonemidae).

Discussion – *Moseria* Bálint, 2022 is a junior homonym of four available generic names; the oldest one of them, *Moseria* Ghigi, 1909 (GHIGI 1909), is currently valid. Accordingly, the replacement name *Moseralfia* nom. nov. is proposed here for *Moseria* Bálint, 2022. Similarly to *Moseria* Bálint, 2022, the replacement name is also dedicated to Alfred Moser (São Leopoldo, Brazil), eminent researcher of Neotropical Lepidoptera.

Pseudogyris Braby et Müller, 2022

Pseudogyris Braby et Müller, 2022 (March) (BRABY & MÜLLER 2022: 3).

Type species by original designation: *Ogyris meeki* Rothschild, 1900.

Szentivanya Bálint, 2022 (September) (BÁLINT 2022: 99). Type species by original designation: *Ogyris meeki* Rothschild, 1900. Junior homonym of *Szentivanya* Kaszab, 1958 (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae); junior objective synonym of *Pseudogyris* Braby et Müller, 2022.

Discussion – *Szentivanya* Bálint, 2022 is a junior homonym of *Szentivanya* Kaszab, 1958 (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) (KASZAB 1958). As it is also a junior objective synonym of *Pseudogyris* Braby et Müller, 2022 (published on 18 March) (BRABY & MÜLLER 2022), both being based on the same type species, there is no need for a replacement name.

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REFERENCES

- BÁLINT ZS. 2022: Függlék. Az új tribuszok, génuszok és fajok leírása. [Appendix. Description of new species, genera and tribes.] – In: D’ABRERA B. & BÁLINT ZS. (eds): *Pillangóvilág. Bevezetés és a teremtett sokféleség rendje*. [World Butterflies. Introduction and order of created diversity.] – Pytheas Könyvmanufaktúra, Budapest, pp. 85–105.
- BRABY M. F. & MÜLLER C. 2022: *Pseudogyris* gen. nov. (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae), a new genus for two rare thecline butterflies from New Guinea, including the description of a new species. – *Tropical Lepidoptera Research* 32(1): 1–15.

- D'ABRERA B. & BÁLINT Zs. 2022: *Pillangóvilág. Bevezetés és a teremtett sokféleség rendje.* [World Butterflies. Introduction and order of created diversity.] – Pytheas Könyvmanufaktúra, Budapest, 111 pp.
- GHIGI A. 1909: Raccolte planctoniche fatte dalla R. Nave “Liguria” nel viaggio di circonnavigazione del 1903–1905. I. Ctenofori. – *Pubblicazioni del R. Istituto di Studi Superiori Pratici e di Perfezionamento in Firenze Sezione di Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* **2**: 1–24.
- KASZAB Z. 1958: Einige neue Tenebrioniden aus den papuanischen Inseln (Coleoptera). – *Idea (Jakarta)* **11**: 1–13.